

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Here is the latest issue of J.UCS. As was already the case with the January issue, only the abstracts of the published papers are accessible free of charge. If you want to read the full-length papers you have to sign up for a subscription for yourself or your organisation. Please, hurry up and do so! You can find all pertinent information under http://www.iicm.edu/jucs_news

We have a number of institutional subscriptions, so far, but not as many as I would like to have, and only a few personal ones! Please spread the word and help to get more subscriptions for J.UCS. In the long run, if we don't get a sufficient base of subscribers J.UCS will lose its appeal!

The forthcoming March issue is a special issue on "Information Technology and Organizational Change", edited by Patricia Carlson from Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology, Indiana, USA - do not lose the opportunity to read it!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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